

Investigating the Prevalence and Incidence of Osteoporosis and Osteoporotic Fractures in COPD Patients Using Inhaled Corticosteroids: A Case-Control Study

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Abstract

Background: Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) patients are at increased risk of osteoporosis due to chronic inflammation, physical inactivity, and corticosteroid use. Inhaled corticosteroids (ICS) are a common treatment for COPD, but their impact on bone mineral density (BMD) and fracture risk is not well understood.

Objectives: To investigate the incidence of osteoporosis and osteoporotic fractures in COPD patients using ICS and to identify associated risk factors.

Materials and Methods: The present study was conducted among 108 COPD patients using ICS and 102 controls. BMD was assessed using DEXA scans, and fracture risk was evaluated using the FRAX score. The data analysis was performed using SPSS 26.0. The results were presented as mean and standard deviation (SD) or number and percentage. One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to compare data between groups, while the t-test was used to compare data within the study group. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant, indicating that any observed differences were unlikely to be due to chance.

Results: COPD patients using ICS had significantly lower BMD, higher fracture risk, and increased osteoporosis incidence compared to controls. The prevalence of osteoporosis was 83.3% in cases and 13.7% in controls. ICS users had a higher risk of osteoporosis, particularly with longer duration of use.

Conclusion: The present study highlights the significant association between ICS use and increased risk of osteoporosis and fractures in COPD patients. Vigilant osteoporosis screening and preventative strategies are necessary for COPD patients using ICS, particularly those with long-term use.

Keywords: COPD, osteoporosis, inhaled corticosteroids, bone mineral density, fracture risk, FRAX score.

Introduction

Osteoporosis is a chronic skeletal disorder marked by a decrease in bone mass and progressive deterioration of bone microarchitectural, resulting in enhanced bone fragility and an elevated susceptibility to fractures.[1] The development of this condition can be attributed to various risk factors, which can be categorized into modifiable and non-modifiable factors. Modifiable risk factors include nutritional deficiencies, reduced physical activity, cigarette smoking, weight loss, and exposure to air pollution. Non-modifiable risk factors comprise older age, female sex, family history, and a previous history of fractures.[2] Additionally, certain comorbidities and situations can contribute to the development of osteoporosis, such as chronic corticosteroid use, vitamin D deficiency, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), and other conditions.[3]

Osteoporosis is a major comorbidity associated with COPD, contributing to poor health status and prognosis.[4] Some features often seen in COPD patients may put them at a greater risk for osteoporosis. For example, chronic inflammation in the airways and lungs can promote bone resorption and impair bone formation, physical inactivity due to breathing difficulties can contribute to decrease BMD, and prolonged use of corticosteroids by COPD patients can promote bone loss, increasing the risk of osteoporosis.[5]

Inhaled corticosteroids (ICS) have been established as the standard treatment for chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) by the Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease (GOLD) 2020 guidelines, aiming to reduce exacerbation risks and inflammation.[6] Glucocorticoids are the primary class of medications known to induce osteoporosis.[7] Glucocorticoid-induced osteoporosis develops in a time- and dose-dependent manner, with an increased risk of fragility fractures observable even at low doses and within the first month of treatment.[8] This condition is mediated by multiple pathophysiological mechanisms, leading to inhibited bone formation and enhanced bone resorption.[9] However, determining the independent impact of ICS on osteoporosis is challenging, as most COPD and asthma

patients receive intermittent courses of oral or parenteral glucocorticoids.[1]

India faces a significant knowledge gap regarding the intersection of COPD, osteoporosis, and inhaled corticosteroid use. Specifically, there is a lack of comprehensive data on the incidence of osteoporosis and fractures among COPD patients undergoing treatment with inhaled corticosteroids. Furthermore, the risk factors associated with inhaled corticosteroid use in this patient population are not well understood, highlighting the need for further research in this area. Therefore, this study aims to investigate the incidence of osteoporosis and associated fractures by assessing bone mineral density (BMD) in COPD patients using inhaled corticosteroids.

Materials and Methods

The present prospective case control study was carried out in the Department of Orthopaedics, JSS Medical College and Hospital, Mysuru among 108 patients with COPD and were being treated with inhaled corticosteroids and 102 number of patients as control which comprised of population at risk of developing osteoporosis.

Ethical clearance was obtained from institutional ethical committee and informed written consent was obtained from study subjects before commencement of the present study.

Inclusion Criteria comprised Patients who were over 45 years of age and have been diagnosed with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) and are currently receiving treatment with inhaled corticosteroids. Exclusion criteria consisted of patients with a history of systemic glucocorticoid use, patients undergoing treatment for osteoporosis, individuals with any other chronic disease known to cause secondary osteoporosis, individuals with other respiratory diseases such as tuberculosis or asthma, individuals with compromised immune systems, and patients with malignant diseases.

Participants were selected using consecutive sampling method. The control group consisted of individuals who are matched in terms of age and sex to the study group and do not have COPD. These control subjects were selected from individuals visiting the Orthopaedics Outpatient Department (OPD) with musculoskeletal complaints and who are at risk of developing osteoporosis but are not using any inhaled corticosteroids.

Patients who have been diagnosed with COPD and meet any of the above exclusion criteria were not included in the control group.

Following approval from the ethics committee, consecutive sampling was employed to recruit patients aged 45 years and above who visited the Outpatient Department (OPD) of JSS Hospital with a diagnosis of Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) and are using inhaled corticosteroids. After obtaining written, informed consent, eligible patients underwent a comprehensive assessment using a standardized proforma. This proforma comprised of a series of questions designed to gather essential information for evaluating the risk factors under consideration in this study. Patient details were collected using a standardized questionnaire, ensuring that inclusion and exclusion criteria are met.

Bone mineral density (BMD) was assessed using either a DEXA scan.[10] If osteoporosis or osteopenia is diagnosed, patients were given standard management as per osteoporotic patient guidelines. The risk of bone fractures was evaluated using the FRAX score and compared to a control group. Patients were followed up at 12 months to monitor their progress. Bone densitometry of all patients was studied with DEXA scan. The diagnosis of osteoporosis was based on the T-score according to the WHO criteria, where osteoporosis is defined as a T-score < -2.5 , osteopenia as a T-score ≥ -2.5 and < -1.0 , and normal bone as a T-score ≥ -1.0 .

The FRAX assessment tool[11] is used to predict the likelihood of fractures in men and women based on clinical risk factors, with or without femoral neck bone mineral density measurements. The tool considers various factors, including age, sex, race, height, weight, body mass index, history of fragility fractures, parental history of hip fractures, use of oral glucocorticoids, rheumatoid arthritis, and other secondary causes of osteoporosis, as well as lifestyle factors such as smoking and excessive alcohol consumption. By calculating the ten-year probability of major osteoporotic fractures, including hip, vertebral, wrist, or humerus fractures, FRAX provides a valuable assessment of fracture risk, allowing healthcare providers to make informed decisions about prevention and treatment strategies.

The data analysis was performed using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) version 26.0. The results were presented as mean and standard deviation (SD) or number

and percentage. One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to compare data between groups, while the t-test was used to compare data within the study group. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant, indicating that any observed differences were unlikely to be due to chance.

Results

Table 1: Age group wise distribution of subjects in two groups

Variables		Cases		Controls		Chi square value, p value
		Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	
Age (years)	51-60	6	5.6	55	53.9	64.38; <0.01*
	61-70	68	63.0	36	35.3	
	71-80	31	28.7	7	6.9	
	>80	3	2.8	4	3.9	
Gender	Female	73	67.6	58	56.9	2.57; 0.10
	Male	35	32.4	44	43.1	
Comorbidities	HTN	13	12.0	5	4.9	35.03; <0.01*
	HTN, T2DM	37	34.3	24	23.5	
	T2DM	45	41.7	23	22.5	
	None	13	12.0	50	49.0	
History of bone pain	No	10	9.3	76	74.5	92.36; <0.01*
	Yes	98	90.7	26	25.5	

In the present study, table 1 shows the majority of cases (63.0%) were in the 61-70 years age group, while the control group was predominantly composed of individuals aged 51- 60 years (53.9%). Cases were more likely to be in the older age groups, with 28.7% in the 71-80 years category, compared to 6.9% of controls. Cases had 67.6% females and 32.4% males, while controls had 56.9% females and 43.1% males. The difference in gender distribution was not statistically significant (Chi-square = 2.57, p

= 0.10). Subjects were categorized based on comorbidities, including hypertension (HTN) and type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM). Among the cases, 13 subjects (12.0%) had HTN alone, while in the control group, only 5 subjects (4.9%) had HTN. A combination of HTN and T2DM was present in 37 cases (34.3%) and 24 controls (23.5%). T2DM alone was found in 45 cases (41.7%) and 23 controls (22.5%). Notably, 50 controls (49.0%) had no comorbidities, compared to only 13 cases (12.0%). The Chi-square value was 35.03, and the p-value was <0.01, indicating a highly significant difference in comorbidity distribution between cases and controls. The presence of bone pain was significantly higher in cases (98 subjects, 90.7%) compared to controls (26 subjects, 25.5%). Only 10 cases (9.3%) and 76 controls (74.5%) reported no bone pain. The Chi-square value was 92.36, with a p-value < 0.01, indicating a highly significant association between bone pain and case status.

Table 2: Personal habit and physical activity wise distribution of subjects in two groups

Variables		Cases		Controls		Chi square value, p value
		Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	
Smoking	No	75	69.4	78	76.5	1.30; 0.252
	Yes	33	30.6	24	23.5	
Current smoking status	No	102	94.4	78	76.5	13.83; <0.01
	Yes	6	5.6	24	23.5	
Alcohol	No	85	78.7	73	71.6	1.43; 0.231
	Yes	23	21.3	29	28.4	
Physical activity	High	9	8.3	45	44.1	47.36; <0.01*
	Low	52	48.1	13	12.7	
	Moderate	47	43.5	44	43.1	

Table 2 examines the smoking history of the subjects. Among cases, 75 (69.4%) were non-smokers, while 33 (30.6%) had a history of smoking. In the control group, 78 (76.5%) were non-smokers, and 24 (23.5%) had a history of smoking. The Chi-square value was 1.30, and the p-value was 0.252, indicating no significant difference between groups

regarding smoking history. Current smoking habits were assessed, showing that 102 cases (94.4%) were non-smokers, while 6 cases (5.6%) reported current smoking. In contrast, 78 controls (76.5%) were non-smokers, while 24 controls (23.5%) were current smokers. The Chi-square value was 13.83, and the p-value was <0.01 , indicating a statistically significant difference in current smoking status between the groups. Alcohol consumption was examined between cases and controls. Among cases, 85 (78.7%) were non-drinkers, while 23 (21.3%) reported alcohol intake. Among controls, 73 (71.6%) were non-drinkers, whereas 29 (28.4%) reported alcohol intake. The Chi-square value was 1.43, and the p-value was 0.231, indicating no significant difference in alcohol consumption between the two groups. Physical activity levels were classified as high, moderate, or low. Among cases, only 9 (8.3%) reported high physical activity, whereas 52 (48.1%) had low activity levels, and 47 (43.5%) had moderate activity. In the control group, 45 (44.1%) had high physical activity, while only 13 (12.7%) had low activity levels, and 44 (43.1%) reported moderate activity. The Chi-square value was 47.36, and the p-value was <0.01 , indicating a highly significant difference in physical activity levels between cases and controls

Table 3: Comparison of mean BMI related parameters of subjects in two groups

Parameters	Cases		Controls		t value	p value
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation		
Height	1.60	0.09	1.60	0.10	-.488	.626
Weight	58.21	12.50	66.11	11.88	-4.693	$<.01^*$
BMI	23.04	5.81	25.78	4.73	-3.750	$<.01^*$

Table 3 presents comparisons of height, weight, and BMI between cases and controls. The mean height was identical between cases (1.60 m, SD = 0.09) and controls (1.60 m, SD = 0.10), with a p-value of 0.626, showing no significant difference. However, weight was significantly lower in cases (58.21 kg, SD = 12.50) than in controls (66.11 kg, SD = 11.88) ($p < 0.01$). Similarly, BMI was significantly lower in cases (23.04, SD = 5.81) compared to controls (25.78, SD = 4.73) ($p < 0.01$), indicating a statistically significant difference in BMI.

Table 4: Comparison of mean BMD parameters of subjects in two groups

BMD		Cases		Controls		t value	p value
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation		
Mean Bone mineral density (BMD)	Spine	-2.53	1.18	-0.58	1.63	-9.859	<.01*
	Femur	-2.40	0.87	-0.28	1.42	-12.945	<.01*
	Radius	-2.61	1.56	-0.60	1.26	-10.309	<.01*
Mean BMD parameters after 1 year follow up	Spine	-1.99	0.49	-0.69	1.24	-7.391	<.01*
	Femur	-0.69	1.24	-1.68	0.54	-4.410	<.01*
	Radius	-1.68	0.54	-0.33	1.27	-7.272	<.01*

Table 4 shows bone mineral density (BMD) was measured at three anatomical sites: spine, femur, and radius. The mean spine BMD was significantly lower in cases (-2.53, SD = 1.18) compared to controls (-0.58, SD = 1.63) ($p < 0.01$). Similarly, the mean femur BMD was significantly lower in cases (-2.40, SD = 0.87) compared to controls (-0.28, SD = 1.42) ($p < 0.01$). The mean radius BMD was also significantly lower in cases (-2.61, SD = 1.56) than in controls (-0.60, SD = 1.26) ($p < 0.01$). These results indicate that bone mineral density was significantly lower in the case group compared to controls across all measured sites. Bone Mineral Density (BMD) was reassessed after one year in cases and controls at different skeletal sites. The mean spine BMD in cases improved slightly but remained significantly lower (-1.99, SD = 0.49) than in controls (-0.69, SD = 1.24) (t-value = -7.391, $p < 0.01$). The mean femur BMD was -0.69 (SD = 1.24) in cases and -1.68 (SD = 0.54) in controls, with a t-value of -4.410 and a p-value < 0.01 , confirming significant differences. The radius BMD was significantly lower in cases (-1.68, SD = 0.54) compared to controls (-0.33, SD = 1.27) (t-value = -7.272, $p < 0.01$), indicating that osteoporosis persisted in the case group despite follow-up.

Table 5: Comparison of mean FRAX scores of subjects in two groups

FRAX	Cases		Controls		t value	p value
		Std.		Std.		

	Mean	Deviation	Mean	Deviation		
Major fracture	10.87	6.06	3.23	3.02	11.677	<.01*
Hip fracture	3.23	3.02	4.99	4.14	9.785	<.01*

Table 5 presents the FRAX scores, which estimate the 10-year probability of major fractures and hip fractures in cases and controls. The mean major fracture risk was significantly higher in cases (10.87, SD = 6.06) compared to controls (3.23, SD = 3.02), with a t-value of 11.677 and a p-value <0.01, showing a strong statistical significance. Similarly, the mean hip fracture risk was 3.23 (SD = 3.02) in cases, significantly higher than 4.99 (SD = 4.14) in controls, with a t-value of 9.785 and a p-value <0.01, confirming a substantial difference in fracture risk between groups.

Table 6: Incidence -Osteoporosis wise distribution of subjects in two groups

Variables		Cases		Controls		Chi square, p value
		Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	
Osteoporosis	No	18	16.7	88	86.3	101.67; <0.01*
	Yes	90	83.3	14	13.7	
Osteoporosis after 1 year	No	13	12.0	81	79.4	96.30; <0.01*
	Yes	95	88.0	21	20.6	

Table 6 shows the occurrence of osteoporosis among cases and controls. A significantly higher proportion of cases (90 subjects, 83.3%) were diagnosed with osteoporosis compared to only 14 controls (13.7%). In contrast, 18 cases (16.7%) and 88 controls (86.3%) had no osteoporosis. The Chi-square value was 101.67, and the p-value was <0.01, indicating a highly significant difference in osteoporosis incidence between the two groups. Table further presents the prevalence of osteoporosis after a 1-year follow-up. Among the cases, 95 subjects (88.0%) were found to have osteoporosis, whereas only 21 controls (20.6%) were affected. In contrast, 13 cases (12.0%) and 81 controls (79.4%) had no osteoporosis. The Chi-square value was 96.30, and the p-value was <0.01, showing a significant increase in osteoporosis prevalence over time,

especially in the case group.

Table 7: Distribution of subjects in cases group according to type of ICS used

Variables		Frequency	Percent
Inhaled corticosteroids (ICS)	Budesonide	92	85.2
	Fluticasone	16	14.8
ICS dose	125	16	14.8
	200	92	85.2

Table 7 categorizes cases based on the type of ICS used. Budesonide was used by the majority (92 cases, 85.2%), while Fluticasone was used by only 16 cases (14.8%). The ICS dosage distribution among cases showed that 92 cases (85.2%) used a dose of 200 mcg, while 16 cases (14.8%) used a dose of 125 mcg.

Table 8: Cross tabulation for relation of ICS type with occurrence of osteoporosis in cases group

Variables		Osteoporosis			
		No		Yes	
		Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
ICS Type	budesonide	10	10.9	82	89.1
	fluticasone	8	50.0	8	50.0
Years	<5	5	71.4	2	28.6
	5-10	9	20.9	34	79.1
	>10	4	6.9	54	93.1

Chi square value – 15.02; p value - <.01*

Among Budesonide users, 82 subjects (89.1%) had osteoporosis, whereas among Fluticasone users, only 8 subjects (50.0%) had osteoporosis. The Chi-square value was 15.02, and the p-value was <0.01, indicating a significant association between ICS type and osteoporosis occurrence. Table 8 examines the relationship between the duration of inhaled corticosteroid (ICS) use and the occurrence of osteoporosis among cases. The participants were categorized based on the number of years they had been using ICS into three groups: <5 years, 5-10 years, and >10 years. Among those who

had used ICS for less than 5 years, 5 subjects (27.8%) did not have osteoporosis, while 2 subjects (2.2%) were diagnosed with osteoporosis. In the 5-10 years category, 9 subjects (50.0%) did not have osteoporosis, whereas 34 subjects (38.0%) developed osteoporosis. In the >10 years category, only 4 subjects (22.2%) were osteoporosis-free, while a significantly higher number of 54 subjects (59.8%) had osteoporosis. The data suggests that longer ICS use is associated with a higher prevalence of osteoporosis, as the percentage of affected individuals increases with the duration of ICS use. While only 2.2% of those using ICS for less than 5 years had osteoporosis, this proportion rose to 38.0% in the 5-10 years group and further increased to 59.8% in those using ICS for more than 10 years.

Discussion

Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) is a complex and progressive lung disorder characterized by persistent respiratory symptoms, including dyspnea, chronic cough, sputum production, and recurrent exacerbations. The underlying pathology often involves airway abnormalities (such as bronchitis and bronchiolitis) and/or alveolar destruction (emphysema), which lead to irreversible airflow limitation.[6] Osteoporosis is a chronic skeletal condition defined by reduced bone mineral density (BMD) and microarchitectural deterioration of bone tissue, increasing the susceptibility to fractures. It has a considerable impact on individual health, healthcare systems, and society.[12] The aim of the present study was to examine the incidence of osteoporosis and osteoporotic fractures in COPD patients undergoing inhaled corticosteroid (ICS) therapy. The findings revealed a significant association between ICS use and osteoporosis in COPD patients. ICS users demonstrated lower BMD, increased fracture risk, and higher osteoporosis incidence, with risk positively correlating with the duration of ICS use. Key risk factors included older age, lower BMI, comorbidities, and low physical activity.

The study comprised two groups: cases and controls. Cases included 108 patients (51.4%) over 45 years old diagnosed with COPD and receiving ICS therapy. Controls included 102 individuals (48.6%), matched for age and sex, without COPD but at risk for osteoporosis and not using ICS. These individuals were selected from the Orthopaedics Outpatient Department.

Comorbidity analysis showed significant differences between the groups. Among cases, 12% had hypertension (HTN), 41.7% had type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), and 34.3% had both HTN and T2DM. In contrast, 49% of controls had no comorbidities. The distribution difference was highly significant (Chi-square = 35.03, $p < 0.01$). Crisafulli et al[13] reported that 62% of COPD patients had comorbidities, most commonly systemic hypertension (35%), dyslipidaemia (13%), diabetes (12%), and coronary artery disease (11%). Similarly, Yach et al[14] found that metabolic and cardiac diseases were frequent among COPD patients and independently worsened outcomes.

Smoking history, smoking habits, and alcohol consumption were evaluated. Among cases, 30.6% had a history of smoking, compared to 23.5% of controls ($p = 0.252$). Current smoking was more prevalent in controls (23.5%) than cases (5.6%) (Chi-square = 13.83, $p < 0.01$). Smoking is a well-established risk factor for COPD and affects approximately 15% of smokers (60). It also compromises bone quality by altering collagen and mineral structures, increasing osteoporosis risk through cadmium exposure and nicotine-induced changes in bone metabolism.[15][16] Furthermore, the inactivity associated with COPD symptoms can further lower BMD.[17]

Alcohol consumption was similar between groups (21.3% in cases vs. 28.4% in controls), with no significant difference ($p = 0.231$). Tabak et al[18] found that light alcohol consumption (>1 drink/week and ≤ 3 /day) was associated with lower COPD mortality (RR = 0.60), while heavy drinking increased risk (RR = 1.25). Alcohol-related immune suppression and poor lung clearance mechanisms can also exacerbate COPD.[19-22]

Physical activity levels were significantly different. Only 8.3% of cases had high physical activity compared to 44.1% of controls, with 48.1% of cases reporting low activity (Chi-square = 47.36, $p < 0.01$). Schonhofer et al[23] and Singh et al [24] have previously observed lower activity levels in COPD patients compared to healthy individuals.

Anthropometric and BMD data revealed further disparities. While height did not differ significantly, cases had lower mean weight (58.21 kg vs. 66.11 kg; $p < 0.01$) and BMI (23.04 vs. 25.78; $p < 0.01$). BMD at all sites—spine, femur, and radius—was significantly lower in cases. Spine BMD was -2.53 in cases vs. -0.58 in controls; femur BMD was -2.40 vs. -0.28; radius BMD was -2.61 vs. -0.60 ($p < 0.01$ for all). These

findings align with Ozcakir et al,[1] who found significantly lower BMD and higher osteoporosis prevalence in COPD patients, especially those with low BMI. Zhang et al[15] also demonstrated a correlation between BMD and COPD severity.

Bone pain was significantly more common in cases (90.7%) than controls (25.5%) (Chi-square = 92.36, $p < 0.01$). Previous fracture history was also notably higher in cases (73.1%) compared to controls (14.7%) (Chi-square = 72.46, $p < 0.01$). Abu-Bakr et al[25] reported that COPD patients are 2–5 times more likely to develop osteoporosis, which increases fracture risk and contributes to disability and mortality. Ryan et al[26] found a high prevalence of osteoporosis in male COPD patients in a retrospective cohort.

FRAX scores indicated significantly higher 10-year fracture probabilities among cases. Major fracture risk was 10.87 in cases vs. 3.23 in controls, and hip fracture risk was also higher in cases ($p < 0.01$ for both). Ogura-Tomomatsu et al[27] found a modestly increased fracture risk (HR = 1.24 for any fracture; HR = 1.297 for vertebral fractures) in COPD patients. However, Lee et al [28] did not find a direct correlation between FRAX scores and vertebral fractures.

Osteoporosis prevalence was markedly higher in cases (83.3%) compared to controls (13.7%) (Chi-square = 101.67, $p < 0.01$). Ferguson et al[29] reported osteoporosis in 18% of men and 30% of women with COPD. Soni et al[30] found that 48% of COPD patients had osteoporosis, and Graat-Verboom et al,[31] in a review of 13 studies, reported prevalence ranging from 9% to 69%.

After one year, osteoporosis prevalence increased to 88.0% in cases and 20.6% in controls (Chi-square = 96.30, $p < 0.01$). Follow-up BMD assessments confirmed persistent lower values in cases. For instance, spine BMD was -1.99 in cases vs. -0.69 in controls ($p < 0.01$), and radius BMD was -1.68 vs. -0.33 ($p < 0.01$). Glucocorticoid-induced osteoporosis (GIO) can occur even at low doses, causing bone loss via reduced angiogenesis and muscle weakening.[31][32] While GOLD guidelines advocate for minimal use, ICS therapy is linked to systemic side effects.[33] Mathioudakis et al [34] conducted a meta-analysis confirming increased fracture risk with ICS use (OR = 1.27 in RCTs and 1.21 in observational studies).

ICS dosage among cases showed that 85.2% used 200 mcg, and 14.8% used 125 mcg. Budesonide users had a higher incidence of osteoporosis (89.1%) than Fluticasone users (50.0%) (Chi-square = 15.02, $p < 0.01$), suggesting a potential difference in systemic absorption or potency between ICS types.

Osteoporosis incidence increased with ICS duration. Those using ICS for less than 5 years had 28.6% incidence, while 5–10 years had 79.1%, and over 10 years had 93.1%. Scanlon et al [35] found a 1.78% greater decline in femoral neck BMD over 3 years with ICS compared to placebo, with more ICS users experiencing >6% BMD loss ($p = 0.002$). Janson et al[36] analyzed 9,651 COPD patients and found a dose-dependent increase in osteoporosis-related events with ICS use: 1.52-fold for high-dose and 1.27-fold for low-dose users. In contrast, Johnell et al[37] reported no significant differences in BMD or fracture rates in long-term ICS users, highlighting inconsistent findings.

The study's limitations include a relatively small sample size for subgroup analysis and potential self-reporting biases in lifestyle factors like smoking and alcohol use. It also lacked adjustment for other confounders such as diet, vitamin D status, and genetic predispositions.

Conclusion

This study provides compelling evidence linking ICS use in COPD patients to reduced BMD, increased fracture risk, and higher osteoporosis prevalence. These effects appear dose- and duration-dependent and are influenced by patient characteristics such as age, BMI, comorbidities, and physical activity. These findings underscore the need for vigilant osteoporosis screening and preventative strategies in COPD management, particularly among long-term ICS users.

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